

**STRUCTURAL EVOLUTION OF
A SUBDUCTED CONTINENTAL CRUST:
THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT (NW IBERIA)**

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GEOLOGICAL SETTING

THE VARISCAN BELT

GONDWANA

Vs

LAURUSSIA

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

THE ALLOCHTHONOUS COMPLEXES OF GALICIA

THE BASAL UNITS

THE MORE EXTERNAL MARGIN OF GONDWANA

THE BASAL UNITS

TWO METASEDIMENTARY SEQUENCES

(Lithostratigraphy and U-Pb in detrital zircons)

THE LOWER SEQUENCE

LATE NEOPROTEROZOIC

AVALONIAN-CADOMIAN ARC-SYSTEM

THE BASAL UNITS

TWO METASEDIMENTARY SEQUENCES

(Lithostratigraphy and U-Pb in detrital zircons)

THE UPPER SEQUENCE

MIDDLE-LATE CAMBRIAN

BACK-ARC BASIN

ARC BUILT ON THE GONDWANA MARGIN

ME

THE BASAL UNITS

TWO METASEDIMENTARY SEQUENCES

(Lithostratigraphy and U-Pb in detrital zircons)

THE UPPER SEQUENCE

MIDDLE-LATE CAMBRIAN

BACK-ARC BASIN

ARC BUILT ON THE GONDWANA MARGIN

MAGMATISM RELATED TO ITS ACTIVITY AND DRIFT

UPPER SEQUENCE: INTERBEDDED BASALTS

CALC-ALKALINE GRANITES

ALKALINE GRANITES

PERALKALINE GRANITES

BASIC ROCKS

LOWER SEQUENCE:
(intruded)

THE BASAL UNITS

THE MORE EXTERNAL MARGIN OF GONDWANA WAS SUBDUCTED BENEATH LAURUSSIA AND THE OPHIOLITHIC UNITS AT THE ONSET OF THE VARISCAN OROGENY

**HIGH-PRESSURE
LOW-MEDIUM TEMPERATURE
METAMORPHISM**

LOWER SEQUENCE-SHEET
ECLOGITE TO BLUESCHIST FACIES

UPPER SEQUENCE-SHEET
BLUESCHIST FACIES

BLUESCHIST FACIES

THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

THE SOUTHERN HALF OF THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

**THE MAPPING OF THE GNEISS
BODIES REVEALS THE
MACROSTRUCTURAL
EVOLUTION
DURING THE EXHUMATION**

THE SOUTHERN HALF OF THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

3D RENDERING

**CALC-ALKALINE
GNEISSES**

THE SOUTHERN HALF OF THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

3D RENDERING

**PERALKALINE
GNEISSES**

**CALC-ALKALINE
GNEISSES**

THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

THE CENTRAL PART OF THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

THE NORTHERN HALF OF THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

THE NORTHERN HALF OF THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

**THE FERVENZA
THRUST**

BUT THEY ARE HERE

**THE MYLONITES
ARE NOT AFFECTED BY
RECUMBENT FOLDS HERE**

THE NORTHERN HALF OF THE MALPICA-TUI UNIT

THE ÓRDENES COMPLEX

THE LALÍN-FORCAREI THRUST

RECONSTRUCTION OF THE TRAIN OF RECUMBENT FOLDS

OUT-OF-SEQUENCE THRUSTS DETACHMENTS..... AND MIGMATITIC DOMES

TECTONIC MODEL

.... AND LATER ON, THE STRIKE-SLIP TECTONICS